

Insights into physiology and metabolic capabilities of *Pediococcus* spp: The Whole genome sequence of nine strains isolated from Yucatan saline environments.

Rojas Herrera, R.A., Serrano-Gamboa J.G., González-Burgos, A., Escalante-Réndiz, D.Y., Rivera-Solís R., Cabañas-Vargas, D., and Sánchez-González, M.N*.

Facultad de Ingeniería Química. Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán. Periférico Norte, Kilómetro 33.5, Tablaje Catastral 13615. Chuburná de Hidalgo Inn, Mérida, Yucatán, México. C.P. 97203.

*To whom correspondence should be addressed

Email: monica.sanchez@correo.uady.mx

Abstract

Nine microorganisms identified as part of the genus *Pediococcus*, were isolated from sediments of Yucatan wetlands and coastal marshes with salinities ranging from 8 to 296 g/kg. Lactic acid bacteria are commonly isolated from nutrient-rich environments such as fermented foods, dairy products, and the gut of various organisms. To explore their physiology, metabolic capabilities, and biotechnological potential, we report here the draft genomes of nine *Pediococcus* strains.

The total genome size ranged between 1.8 and 2.1 Mb, while the total number of contigs was highly variable (between 14 and 167). The smallest contig N50 was 296.2 kb while the largest was 445.2 kb. The GC content was about 42 for isolates identified as *P. acidilactici* and about 37 for isolates identified as *P. pentosaceus*.

These data will provide a useful resource for future studies on the physiology and metabolic capabilities of *Pediococcus* spp and their use in new biotechnological developments.

Genomic sequences were deposited in NCBI GenBank under the BioProject PRJNA1078396

Introduction

Coastal wetlands and marshes are among the most valuable and biologically diverse ecosystems in the world. In the Yucatan peninsula, wetlands cover an area of approximately 563,345 Ha and include areas with high salinity spots (Morales-Ojeda et al., 2021). The

microorganisms inhabiting these environments play important roles mediating the biogeochemical cycling of nutrients and are adapted to survive under extremely harsh conditions such as high salt concentration and oxygen deprivation (Xamxidín et al., 2025). Bacteria isolated from hypersaline environments have great biotechnological potential due to their ability to survive and thrive in extreme conditions (Martínez et al., 2022; Oren, 2010). These microorganisms have developed unique adaptation mechanisms, such as the production of halotolerant enzymes, exopolysaccharides, and compatible compounds that protect them from osmotic stress have been developed by these bacteria (Uma et al., 2020). The enzymes and metabolites produced have applications in the food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and bioremediation industries, as they are capable of functioning in conditions where other biocatalysts would fail. Furthermore, halophilic bacteria can contribute to the development of new strategies for the production of bioplastics and the synthesis of biomolecules with antimicrobial and antioxidant properties (Meglali et al., 2025; Ventosa et al., 2015). All these characteristics make them a promising source of innovation in industrial and environmental biotechnology.

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are a group of Gram-positive bacteria that ferment carbohydrates into lactic acid, which not only preserves food but also enhances its safety, flavor, and nutritional values. Additionally, LAB strains are frequently used as probiotics for promoting gut health and modulating the immune system (Eviúvú et al., 2017). The growing importance and widespread use of probiotics has promoted the search for microorganisms other than *Lactobacillus*, *Clostridium*, *Bifidobacterium*. In this regard, different studies have highlighted the importance of *Pediococcus* in the field of probiotics (Tathode et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2025).

Nutrient-rich environments such as fermented foods, dairy products, and the gut of various organisms are the usual niches of LAB; however, less is known about non-lactic or extreme environments. In our research group, microorganisms belonging to the *Pediococcus* genus were isolated from sediments of Yucatan wetlands and coastal marshes with salinities ranging from 8 to 296 g/kg. Interestingly, isolation was not possible in samples with lower salt concentrations (Escalante-Rendiz, D. et al., 2012). To explore their physiology, metabolic capabilities, and biotechnological potential, we report here the draft genomes of nine *Pediococcus* strains.

Material and Methods

Bacterial Isolates

Pediococcus strains are maintained stored in the Faculty of Chemical Engineering of the Autonomous University of Yucatán. (Table 1) Microorganisms were activated culturing in de Man, Rogosa and Sharpe (MRS) agar, at 37°C under microaerophilic conditions.

Cell preparation and DNA processing was conducted following MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK) strain submission procedures. Subsequent library preparation, DNA sequencing and bioinformatics was conducted by MicrobesNG, following in-house protocols. Genomic DNA libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions with the following modifications: input DNA was increased 2-fold, and PCR elongation time increased to 45 seconds. Libraries were sequenced using the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired-end protocol. Reads were adapter trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. *De novo* assembly was performed on samples using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012), and contigs were annotated using Prokka 1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Results

Trimmed sequence read data and genome assembly data of the *Pediococcus* strains has been deposited in NCBI/GenBank under the BioProject PRJNA1078396. A summary of the genomic features of the nine *Pediococcus* strains is listed in Table 1.

The total genome size ranged between 1.8 and 2.1 Mb, while the total number of contigs was highly variable (between 14 and 167). The smallest contig N50 was 296.2 kb while the largest was 445.2 kb. The GC content was about 42 for isolates identified as *P. acidilactici* and about 37 for isolates identified as *P. pentosaceus*.

Although strains YCO-23, QCH-42 and YCO-17 had previously been classified as *P. pentosaceus* by 16S RNA sequencing (unpublished) they were reclassified as *P. acidilactici* since they are over 97 % identical by average nucleotide identity (ANI) to the best match type-strain genome of *P. acidilactici* (NCBI RefSeq assembly: GCF_012396515.1), with 84.3%, 83.1 and 84.2%, respectively, coverage of the genome.

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Table 1: Statistical summary of the sequences of the nine *Pediococcus* strains isolated from hypersaline environments in Yucatan, Mexico

Strain	Organism	Genome size (Mb)	No. Contigs	Contig N_{50} (kb)	Mean coverage	GC content	GenBank accession		
							BioSample ID	Assembly	Reads
QCH-42	<i>P. acidilactici</i>	2.1	80	343.6	87	42.5	SAMN39999250	JBANEP000000000	SRR28016042
QCH-66	<i>P. acidilactici</i>	2.1	167	445.2	146.9	42.5	SAMN39999251	JBCGHI000000000	SRR28719796
YCO-17	<i>P. acidilactici</i>	2.1	27	445.2	103	42	SAMN39999254	JBANEQ000000000	SRR28016041
YCO-23	<i>P. acidilactici</i>	2.1	14	445.2	150	42	SAMN39999252	JBBDHO000000000	SRR28016045
CAT-100BC	<i>P. pentosaceus</i>	1.8	19	419.3	162.5	37	SAMN39999255	JBCGHK000000000	SRR28719798
QMA-03G	<i>P. pentosaceus</i>	1.8	21	296.2	96	37.5	SAMN39999248	JBALBK000000000	SRR28016044
QMA-24BC	<i>P. pentosaceus</i>	1.8	19	296.2	136.5	37	SAMN39999249	JBCGHH000000000	SRR28719795
QMA-27BC	<i>P. pentosaceus</i>	1.9	109	296.2	694	37.5	SAMN39999246	JBCGHL000000000	SRR28719799
YCO-16	<i>P. pentosaceus</i>	1.8	20	419.3	152.5	37	SAMN39999253	JBCGHJ000000000	SRR28719797